

THE SCIENCE OF BECOMING CRUEL

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Abstract: This work presents the science of becoming cruel. Cases and evidence of cruel scientific activities affecting humans are also presented.

Keywords: Science, psychology, nervous system, evidence.

Introduction

One of the most infamous psychological studies ever conducted was the Stanford Prison Experiment. It's mentioned in almost every Intro to Psychology textbook. They tend to focus on how unethical it was and are less critical of its supposed conclusion.

August 14, 1971. Palo Alta, California. Twelve young men are rounded up from their homes by police, placed under arrest, and brought to a makeshift prison in the basement of Stanford University. It all begins as a study of the psychology of prison life, led by Stanford psychology professor Dr. Philip Zimbardo. 24 volunteers – 12 guards and 12 prisoners,- have agreed to spend the next two weeks recreating life in a correctional facility. The prisoners are no longer individuals, forced to wear smocks, stocking caps and shackles. Identified only by their prison numbers. The guards quickly adapt to their new profession.

Given anonymity by their mirrored sunglasses, some of them start to control the meager food rations, restrict cruel methods. Within just six days of the planned two-weeks study, conditions are so bad, that the entire operation is shut down. The study wakes international headlines. Zimbardo's fame skyrockets, and his conclusions are taught to students worldwide, used as a defense in criminal trials and are even submitted to Congress to explain the abuses inflicted at Aby Ghraib. The study brings up a question just as important then as it is today. Zimbardo's shocking conclusion is that when people feel anonymous and have power over depersonalized others, that can easily become evil. And it occurs more often than we'd like to admit. But while it's true that people were mean to each other during the Stanford Prison Experiment, what if what truly caused that behavior wasn't what we've always been told?

51 Years Later

The Stanford Prison experiment has always had its controversies. But a wave of recent revelations have pushed it back into the spotlight 51 years later. Journalist Bem Blum, who was interviewed in Mind Field TV series says that his involvement into the Stanford Prison Experiment was quite personal. "Like everyone, I had kind of absorbed the basic lesson of the experiment through the cultural ether." His cousin Alex, a 19-year-old U.S Army Ranger was arrested for a bank robbery. "Alex thought the whole thing was a training exercise. He was so brainwashed in this intense Ranger training that when a superior soon proposed this bank robbery, he took it as just one more kind of tactical thought experiment." Dr. Philip Zimbardo participated in Alex's legal defense. He submits a letter to the court, advocating lenience in sentencing on the grounds that Alex, had been so transformed by the social environment of the Ranger battalion that he participated in the bank robbery without exercising his freewill. "Zimbardo was a family hero", - says journalist Bem Blum. The stories' hero-Alex, admits that he knew that that was a bank robbery, but he didn't have the moral courage to back out. Zimbardo has claimed that the guards were put in the situation, where the hidden wellspring of Sandusky that apparently lies in all of us unfolded organically. "The guards now fell into their job"- claims Zimbardo. Psychologists call that "Demand Characteristics." Experimental subjects tend to be motivated to give experimenters what they want.

Michael Stevens concluded that when you tell people to be cruel, they'll do it once you say it's for a greater good, like science. When people are given power, it's easier that we think for abuse to happen. But can anonymity, power, and depersonalization alone lead to evil?

Dr. Jared Bartels a psychologist who has written extensively about the Stanford prison experiment and how it is taught, admits in one of interviews that the piece of this experiment is the role of personality and personality traits. “ Because that saw the word “ prison” that thought,-“ I want to be a part of that.” So how to give people the opportunity to be as evil you have some power differences, you have to have depersonalization.”

I would have been content in detail the ways in which situational forces are more powerful than we think, or that we acknowledge, in shaping our behavior in many contexts. A large body of evidence in social psychology supports the concept that situational power triumphs over individual power in given contexts. A full understanding of the dynamics of human behavior requires that we recognize the extent and limits of personal power, situational power, and systemic power. However, unless we become sensitive to the real power of the System, understand it’s own set of rules and regulations, behavioral change will be transient and situational change illusory. From Zimbardo’s book “ The Lucifer book “,-“ Dehumanization is one of the central processes in the transformation of ordinary, normal people into different or even wanton perpetrators of evil. Dehumanization is like a cortical cataract that clouds one’s thinking and fosters the perception that others people are less than human. It makes some people come to see those others as enemies deserving of torment torture and annihilation. When the bell for “time comes to act” rings, people will know that it rings for them. It sounds a call to uphold what is best in human nature that rises above the powerful pressures of situation and system as the profound assertion of human dignity opposing evil. The question that won’t leave me in peace, is “Am I capable of evil?” “Are we capable of evil?”

We fear evil, but are fascinated by it. As Zimbardo says. –“ Evil consists in intentionally behaving in ways that harm, abuse, demean, dehumanize or destroy innocent others.” In short, it is “knowing better but doing worse.” I believe that every individual has to reflect upon three issues. How well do you really know yourself, your strengths and weaknesses? Does your self- knowledge come from reviewing your behavior in familiar situations or from being exposed to totally new settings where your old habits are challenged? In the same vein, how well do you really know the people with whom you interacts daily, your family, friends, classmates, co-workers?

“Most of us know ourselves only from our limited experiences in familiar situations that involve rules, laws, policies, and pressures constrain us.”

But what happens when we are exposed to totally new and unfamiliar settings where our habits don't suffice? You start a new job, you change your school, join a new team, get arrested, enlist in the military, volunteer for an experiment, or move away from home. Throughout this journey, and perhaps your life I would like you to continually ask the "Me also?" question as we encounter various forms of evil.

Dr. Erick Kandel on one of the Larry King's interviews says, that instinctive inclination leads to becoming an evil. "Some people dislike Jews, no matter what do you tell them. People find it advantageous"

From scientific point of view

Now we know a lot more than we used to know about brain, and turns out that there are a number of areas of the brain, and turns out that that are very important in social-decision- making and moral attitudes. If you think that the brain has a number of main sections like wrinkly cortex- the part that seems to underline thought, but there's a more primitive part of the brain that deals with emotion called the "amygdala", that registers emotion but particularly has an ability to recognize when somebody else out there has a fearful face or is in a state of fright.

So the interesting thing about the kind of cold-hearted murderers is that their amygdala's don't function properly the way ours does. They would recognize the crying kid but they would take advantage of the child, pretend to take it to the information booth to get it reconnected with its mom and then kidnap the kid. So in conclusion the murderer's amygdala functions in a significantly different way. Another important area of the brain is the lower front of the brain called "The

Orbitofrontal cortex.” That area is involved in moral decision-making and figuring out what’s good and what’s wrong, that we learn as we grow up. That area of the brain is not operating at full till it way be possible then to carry out an act which would be repugnant and very much against the law. So the orbitofrontal cortex is kind of braking system, which if it is operating, will put the brakes on a thought or a desire that way have preceded it, which means that if that cortex is not operating, the person will not think of his actions.

Actually there is an interconnection between the amygdala and the frontal cortex, and if that connectivity is not operating properly, the person would go ahead and do the unthinkable actions. Also if the message from “Anterior Cingulate Cortex” is weak, you won’t think of the cons of the action he or she would do.

The line between good and bad is permeable and almost anyone can be induced to cross it when pressured by situational forces. If that’s true, than the Stanford Prison Experiment, like the classical Milgrum study, teaches us an important lesson.

“The mind is its own place and in itself can make a heaven of hell, and hell of heaven.

Conclusion

The article shows that not the situation rises above the personality, but instead the personality rises above the situation. We also learned how that happens, what

parts of the brain can affect people become cruel. It is very vital learning how it happens if we want to improve conditions where power is involved. So this debate is still ongoing which is great. As my favorite educator said, questioning methods and interpretations is not a personal attack. It's how we improve our confidence in what we know. And that's how science works.

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